

Artificial Intelligence-In Defence

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

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Abstract

AI can be understood as the theoretical creation and development of computer systems or algorithms able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence. There is a continuous, controversial debate going on in the Media: on the one hand, about the potential of artificial Intelligence as game changer that will bring huge Benefits to humankind; and, on the other, on the supposed threat it poses to our civilization given that the impact of AI in the future is difficult to evaluate at this time. There are already calls for ethical regulation before we lose control on this technology. Commercial companies making huge profits on the global market are driving innovation in this field and developing new algorithms to provide intelligence through different applications exceeding recognition of images, voice and text.

Citation:

Praveen, D., et al.
“Artificial Intelligence-
In Defence.” *Shanlax
International Journal
of Arts, Science and
Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1,
2018, pp. 226–33.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.1403625](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403625)

Introduction

In the last century, the arrival of digital computers made it possible to perform mathematical operations and data storage at a rate far beyond the capabilities of human beings. It then became possible to develop very complex algorithms and eventually programme machines in a way that allows them to learn and provide solutions comparable to what we call intelligence in human beings. This gave computer based systems the possibility to learn from data, the environment and from their own errors: something known as ‘cognitive computing’.

Deep Learning, a technology based on specific kinds of Neural Networks, is responsible for the quantum leap observed in the field since 2009. It uses data analysis to predict trends and discover hidden information and patterns in the ocean of data provided by existing networks and sensors.

Having identified a number of different ‘layers’ (and generations) of AI, we will now propose to also differentiate between a number of different ‘layers’ (and maybe again also evolutionary mutations) of defense and armed force. When most of us think about the concept of ‘armed force’ today, we conjure up highly hierarchically organized mobile formations of uniformed soldiers equipped with a wide range of industrial-age physical technologies based (mostly) on steel, engines and firepower (tanks, frigates, jet-fighters, etc.), that are employed by national political leaders to control and secure their territory and to defend and/or advance their national goals through the application of (often lethal) industrialkinetic violence.

Layers of 'Defense'

- 'Defense' as military operators ('war fighters' in the parlance of some nations) – e.g. the Netherlands Defense Force (NDF);
- Defense as an organization that supports these operators but also interacts with its counterparts – e.g. the Netherlands Defense Organization (NDO);
- Defense as a player in an increasingly more whole-of-government security oriented approach – e.g. the Netherlands Defense and Security Organizations (NDSO);
- Defense as the (potential) catalyst of a broader defense and security ecosystem of sensors and effectors – e.g. the Netherlands Defense and Security Ecosystem (NDSE)

Indian Army leverages the assistance of CAIR in integrating AI

Ai-powered robots can travel across hazardous terrains, perform remote surgery, and most importantly execute surveillance missions. As they continue to grow more sophisticated, autonomous, and fast, private players and federal agencies are gradually integrating robots within the defense landscape.

Global developments in the Robotics Industry fueled towards enhancing Defence

Most of the advanced defense technologies in the world are robots, and with time the defense industry is gradually shifting towards integrating Ai into the robots they build for military applications. For instance, the military has deployed unmanned autonomous vehicles for reconnaissance (such as detecting anti ship mines in littoral waters), monitoring coastal waters for adversaries (like pirate ships), an precision air strikes on evasive targets.

US based Defense Advanced Research Project Agency, or DARPA, as it is popularly called, operates under the Department of Defense is a pioneer in deploying emerging technologies in defense. The organization was established in 1958 as reaction to the launch of Sputnik, and has

since then pursued areas of interest, considered more extreme than the individual. DARPA officials had earlier released a project called, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), focused on machine learning and human/computer interaction. End-users can understand, trust, and manage the emerging generation of artificial intelligence (AI) systems using XAI.

Moreover, American robot-maker Boston Dynamics could use DARPA’s funding and oversight in building a bipedal humanoid robot, named Atlas. The robot stands 1.8 meter tall, and can execute a variety of search and rescue operations, furnish emergency services, and perform multiple other tasks, in environments where humans can’t possibly survive.

For the time-being, AI is mostly used by the military in non-combatant roles. Artificial Intelligence was leveraged by the States as a part of their two primary operations Desert Storm and Desert Shield, during the events of Gulf War. The U.S. made use of an AI-powered planning tool, called DART. Moreover, projects are being undertaken which involve Development of training simulators incorporating AI.

AI in Other Armed Forces Today

The armed forces of the world’s leading military powers all recognize the qualitative edge AI systems are likely to give them today and tomorrow – soldiers who often “face problems of scale, complexity, pace and resilience that outpace unaided human decision making.”²²⁴ Whether for commanders faced with unconventional adversaries in high speed engagements; intelligence analysts faced with drawing the correct conclusions from peta bytes of noisy data; or frontline soldiers; AI promises to augment analysis and decision-making capabilities and reaction times both, speed up learning, and improve their ability to act with discretion, accuracy, and care under uncertain and changing conditions. It is therefore little surprise that many of world’s leading militaries are running active AI development and deployment programs; however, it is the way these AI systems are tailored to underlying needs, which reveals a lot about the evolving strategic and tactical doctrines of these powers – and the changing nature of deterrence and warfare in the decades to come.

China

As the second biggest ‘player’ in general-purpose AI China is increasingly showing that it is more than capable of keeping pace with the US in this field. While in terms of fundamental breakthroughs, China is still lagging behind the US, there has been a massive increase in growth in terms of cited (machine learning) research.²²⁵ To spur this, in February 2017, China’s National Development and Reform Commission approved a plan to establish an online ‘national laboratory for deep learning’, commissioning Baidu to set up the research effort which will focus on seven

areas of research including machine learning-based visual recognition, voice recognition, new types of human machine interaction and deep learning intellectual property. The overarching goal, it stated, is to “boost China’s overall competence in artificial intelligence”. Meanwhile, major Chinese companies such as Baidu, Alibaba and Tencent have proven remarkably adept at rapidly iterating over breakthroughs to develop – and deploy – applications of this technology, as well as making remarkable home-grown breakthroughs in fields such as speech recognition or self-driving cars.

Israel

Israel was one of the first countries to reveal that it has deployed fully automated robots: self-driving military vehicles to patrol the border with the Palestinian-governed Gaza Strip. Next in the IDF’s plans is to equip the vehicles with weapons, and deploy them in stages to Israel’s frontiers with Egypt, Jordan, Syria, and Lebanon. Meanwhile, the Israeli ‘Harpy’ anti-radiation unmanned aerial vehicle is claimed to already able to detect, target, and engage enemy radar installations without any human oversight or supervision. Further in the future, the military is looking to form mixed combat units of robotic vehicles and human soldiers.

Multi-Application System (UMAS), is “a software-based package that is designed to provide ‘advanced’ control of a ‘variety’ of manned and unmanned applications. As such, it is described as incorporating proprietary artificial intelligence and ‘unique’ interfaces and as offering ‘unrivalled’ levels of system reliability and performance.

Russia While still somewhat lagging behind on its great power rivals in terms of deep machine learning capabilities, the Russian Federation has displayed a steady commitment to developing and deploying a wide range of robotic military platforms, including unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs), with the full backing of its MoD and domestic industries: in January 2017, President Putin called for the creation of “autonomous robotic complexes” for use by the military, previously entrusting the Advanced Research Foundation with the new ‘National Center for the Development of Robotic Technologies and Basic Robotic Components’, in order to consolidate so far uncoordinated efforts for the creation of advanced robotic equipment.

US

As of yet the most prominent actor in the field of military AI, the United States has been actively involved in AI-related R&D since its very emergence of the field.. However, having overseen and driven much of the early breakthroughs in AI research (and computer science broadly) during the Cold War, the bulk of the US’s efforts have now shifted towards deploying these technologies with a clear focus on increasing its armed forces’ operational effectiveness as well as standoff force projection capabilities (A2A in our terminology). In this speech to the Defense One National Security Forum conference, Work identified five pillars to the military future:

1. Autonomous deep learning machine systems which are able to see the patterns through the chaff of hybrid warfare, to give early warning that something is happening in gray zone conflict areas (such as the Ukraine), and which are able to respond at extreme speed, and under rapidly shrinking engagement windows. Such learning systems might, he argues, fill the gap in those fields – such as air defense or cyber defense – where human operators alone cannot achieve sufficient speed to stop or degrade a determined attack.

2. Human machine collaboration, which will include the promotion of so-called ‘Centaur’ warfighting,²⁷⁴ going from the observation that teams combining the strategic analysis of a human with the tactical acuity of a computer, reliably defeat either human-only or computer-only teams across many games.

3. Assisted human operations, whereat wearable electronics, uploadable combat apps; heads up displays, exoskeletons, and other systems, can enable humans on the front line to perform better in combat.

4. Advanced human-machine combat teaming where a human working with unmanned systems is able to take better decisions and undertake cooperative operations. Examples of these are the Army’s Apache and Gray Eagle UAV systems, which are designed to operate in conjunction. Other examples are drone ‘motherships’; electronic warfare networks, or swarming systems which will help transform operations by enabling one mission commander to direct a full swarm of micro-UAVs.

5. Network-enabled semi-autonomous weapons, where systems are both linked, and hardened to survive cyber attack.

All of these systems would be networked together through learning systems, enabling a form of ‘algorithmic warfare’ and a machine-learning approach to targeting.

The Emergence of Private Players in the Landscape

Private players are entering the space, as the U.S. Air Force leverages the assistance of private industry in developing systems which facilitate faster collection and examination of information. ALPHA was initially developed by Psibernetix as training aid for the U.S. Air Force. The AI program has been re-commissioned into friendly co-pilot system to help human pilots using the simulator. The use of AI will help improve reaction and decision making time to implement more effective military actions.

Military-industry partnership, maintained and encouraged through legislative, policy, and organizational innovations will be instrumental to in ensuring the appropriate use of AI for national defense. The federal government must invest towards AI and robotics, depending on the combatant needs. This will help towards developing a world class military technology

Indian Army's Venture into the AI landscape

India has no plans to lag in the race of equipping nations' armed forces with up to-date artificial intelligence (AI) and robots. CAIR is a DRDO lab, leading research in artificial intelligence for India. been working on a project to develop. Multi Agent Robotics Framework (MARF) for more than eight months now. MARF will equip India's armed forces with an array of robots that can function as a team, in fashion similar to what our soldiers do. The AI-powered multi layered architecture is capable of providing multitude of military applications, and will enable collaboration amongst a team of various robots Indian Army has already built Wheeled Robot with Passive Suspension, Snake Robot, Legged Robot, Wall-Climbing Robot, and Robot Sentry, among others.

CAIR has also begun working on a project entailing the development of dependable intelligent mobile robots. This will assist in equipping Indian armed forces with self- reliant, adaptable, and fault-tolerant systems; besides improving robot's' ability to execute tasks autonomously. These robots have been designed to undertake operations in various conditions, both environmental and terrain.

Unmanned systems targeted for military operations could only be enabled by intelligence and mobility. Moreover, India has several types of terrain mountainous, desert, rural, urban, outdoor, and indoor; each presenting its own locomotion challenge to any robotic platform. This impediment could only be tackled by undertaking extensive research in locomotion technologies.

Robotics in Defence

The development in defence technology and the geo-political environments necessitates increased defence spending year by year due to the requirement for weapons and arms. However, the recent trend to replace the convention equipment by robots smart and intelligent machines that learns by observation, trial and error to enhance operational efficiency, are providing costeffective alternative.

AI can provide multiple options for military applications for a strategic, operational and tactical level planning in many of the functions. The beginning has been made with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), Unmanned Ground Systems (UGS) guided bomb and missile systems, increasing ranges and accuracy of the smart ammunition etc. are increasingly preferred. Indian defence services are presently using indigenously designed Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) Daksh for Bomb Disposal, Unmanned Autonomous Vehicles (Netra UAV, Rustom, Searcher etc.) for reconnaissance, other mini robot machines.

Indian Army has placed the order for 200 Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) Daksh robots to defuse explosives. Additionally, DAC has approved approx. 544 Robots for Indian Army from indigenous source.

The robots will be Private sector Robotics and Artificial intelligence in defence can be a new potential sector for the private players. Till now private sector have been focused primarily in making Robots for consumer goods market. Making products for the defence can also have a dual use. There are organization into making Robots of various kind, some of these are TAL manufacturing solution limited, PARI Robotics, Hi-Tech Robotics, KUKA Robotics, Robo soft Systems, Serial Innovations, Fanuc Corporation, Idea Forge amongst others.

Additionally, there are some foreign companies who are in development of this technology. Some specific examples being:

Uran-9, tracked armored vehicle controlled remotely by an operator equipped with 2472 30-millimeter cannon with a rate of fire of 350 to 400 rounds per minute and can shoot high explosive incendiary and armor-piercing ammunition.

Emerging Trend in AI

The next level would be the Robotics with Artificial Intelligence. The future war systems could be dominated by unmanned systems. Artificial Intelligence and Robotics shall have the following applications:

- Image interpretation for target identification and classification.
- Expert systems for diagnosis and maintenance of sophisticated weapon systems such as radars and missiles.
- Robotic equipment can be used to provide precision targeting support and carriage of ammunition and accuracy.
- Camera equipped and shock-resistant platforms to provide fire power remotely are also possible applications.
- Systems for diagnosis and maintenance sophisticated weapon systems
- Missile target range and trajectory analysis for evaluation of kill zones, launch time and simulation to assist in qualifying missile performance in various environments.
- Enhanced use of robots for anti improvised explosive device, extraction of personnel, firing of guns and other applications.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence is highly likely to radically transform our thinking about and our practical approaches towards armed force and defense.

Most of the literature we found on AI and defense is currently concentrated in the top left cell of this table: conveniently ‘narrow’ AI that can help our current operators and warfighters to stay within the current paradigm but to better accomplish their current tasks. We have seen that some of the key military players today – none more than the Artificial Narrow Intelligence Artificial General Intelligence Artificial Super Intelligence ‘Armed Force’ (A2A) Monitor frontrunners and buy opportunistically Review robustness current force structure Ministry of Defense (A2D

and D2D) Identify short-term challenges and opportunities Identify long-term challenges and opportunities Comprehensive (D2G and G2G) Identify short-term challenges and opportunities Identify long-term challenges and opportunitiesCatalyze dialogue with all stakeholders Defense and Security Ecosystem (E2E and E2I)Explore new niches Explore new niches Existential challenges and opportunities: fundamental rethink of defense101HCSS R epoRt United States, but other (aspirational) peer-competitors as well – are focusing primarily on this cell in the table. Based on the recent track record of cost inflation in the A2A option space, the financial implications of focusing on this particular type of defense AI is highly likely to prove exorbitant. Given the Pentagon’s superior financial firepower (which has also just received a significant boosted from the incoming Trump administration), its currently still dominant position in the field of AI, and the peculiar dynamics of its political economy of defense – the investments it is likely to make in this area are – in our assessment – likely to be both substantial and impactful. This means they will yield uniquely new and powerful – even if ‘just’ in the industrial-age sense – capability options that will be expensive but may prove to still provide far better value-for-money than anything European force providers (certainly small- to medium-sized ones) would likely be able to generate in this space in their own right. We therefore recommend a cautiously pragmatic and opportunistic attitude towards this cell of the AI option-space. Investment opportunities will undoubtedly emerge in this segment that small- to medium-sized defense providers might be able to jump on – even with respect to their own R&D funds, but our suggestion here would be to be as opportunistic as our defense industrial basis has been in recent ‘big ticket’ defense procurement projects.

As the overall table and especially the right-downwards orange arrow in Figure 15 suggest, however, we anticipate far superior value-for-money opportunities for SMC DSOs in the other cells of this table – certainly downwards towards the defense and security ecosystem, but arguably even towards the right bottom as we move towards artificial superintelligence. This, then, would require a more sustained and comprehensive debate between the various public and private stakeholders within the broader defense and security ecosystem about what the optimal way would be to ensure defense and security value for money in this day and age. The suggestion we make in this paper, is that we see few other actors within those ecosystems that have similar perspectives and aptitudes than our defense organizations. Our suggestion is not that they should be the ones to execute the various broader defense and security efforts that might emerge from these broader discussions. We do suggest, however, that they might be better positioned than many others to kickstart and catalyze this discussion. The final – existentially important – cell in this option space is the one to right of the option space. Artificial super-intelligence – i.e. intelligence that is superior to that of homo sapiens – is likely to pose quite unique challenges to defense and security planners. We have seen in our longue durée³²¹ historical overview of the nexus between intelligence and defense how the non-physical, purely cognitive part of ‘human force’ proved evolutionarily superior to the sometimes physically stronger but cognitively and socially weaker ‘force’ of other species. If that history is a lesson, then the emergence of super-human intelligence is surely a transition that requires extraordinarily careful human consideration.

Work Sources

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